

Fig. 2. pH titration curves for the ternary complex La-EDTA-Trznc. a=acid curve, L=ligand curve, MA=binary complex (La-EDTA), MAL=ternary complex.

stability. This justifies the negative $\Delta \log K$ values in the present series.

In case of lanthanides, formation of ionic bonds is generally favoured, because overlap with the metal 4f orbitals is difficult due to the shielding effect of 5s and 5p electrons. This would mean that Born relation $E = Z^2/2r(1-1/D)$ should be valid for the complexation equilibrium under study. The stability constants $\log K_{ML}$ as well as $\log K_{MAL}$ being directly proportional to E , the energy change on complexation of the gaseous metal ion should yield linear plots with Z^2/r (Z is charge and r is radius of the metal ion). In the present case such plots (not shown here) show some deviation from a strict linear nature suggesting partial covalency⁶. Earlier work⁶⁻⁹ on lanthanide complexes support our observations.

The log-log plots of $\log K_{MAL}$ vs $\log K_{ML}$ and $\log K_{MA}$ have also been examined. The almost linear plots (not shown) indicate that the process of association of L with [Ln-EDTA] species in the ternary system is the same as the association of L or A with Ln^{3+} in corresponding binary systems. A slight variation is observed which may be due to the ligational nature and steric effect of the secondary ligand.

The $\log K_{ML}$ and $\log K_{MAL}$ values have been correlated with some fundamental properties of lanthanide metal ions, viz., 3rd ionisation potential, charge/size ratio and standard entropies. A linear correlation (not shown) indicates similarity in the nature of complexes. These observations are in agreement with the earlier work¹⁰⁻¹¹ on lanthanide complexes. The $\log K_{ML}$ and $\log K_{MAL}$ values have been found to follow the usual trend¹² with respect to the metal ions i.e. $La^{3+} < Ce^{3+} < Pr^{3+} < Nd^{3+} < Sm^{3+} < Gd^{3+}$.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. A. V. Mahajani, Head, Department of Chemistry for laboratory facilities, and to I. C. I., India for a gift sample of the dye. One of the authors (S. N. L.) is thankful to the U. G. C., New Delhi for the award of a Senior Research Fellowship.

References

1. A. BUTUCHELIA, *Chem. Abs.*, 1970, 93, 133982b.
2. JU. LURIE, "Hand book of Analytical Chemistry", MIR Publications, Moscow, 1975, p. 219.
3. H. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 3897; 1954, 2904.
4. M. H. HASHMI and A. A. AYAZ, *Coun. Sci. Ind. Res. Lahore, Pakistan, Chem. Abs.*, 64, 11976h.; *Analyst*, 1964, 89, 147.
5. T. D. MOELLER, *Chem. Rev.*, 1965, 65, 1.
6. F. H. SPEDLING, J. E. POWEL and E. J. WHEELWRIGHT, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 78, 34.
7. L. K. A. STARELY and T. RANDALL, *Discuss. Faraday Soc.*, 1958, 26, 157.
8. G. P. BENGUPTA and O. R. BERA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, 57, 558.
9. M. S. MAYADRO and S. S. PUROHIT, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, 57, 1017.
10. F. P. DWYER and D. P. MOELLER, "Chelating Agents and Metal Chelates", Academic Press, N.Y., 1964, p. 292.
11. J. K. FOREMAN and T. D. SMITH, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 1752.
12. J. O. BAILAR, "Comprehensive Inorganic Chemistry", Pergamon Press, 1973, p. 7.

Determination of Stability Constant of Copper(II) Complexes with Ethylenediamine and Acetyl Salicylate (Aspirinate) by Electrochemical Methods

RAM DAS, GIRISH DIXIT and (MISS) KAMALA ZUTSHI
Department of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan,
Jaipur-302 004

Manuscript received 9 October 1980, revised 16 October 1981,
accepted 10 December 1981

A number of studies on mixed ligand complex formation has appeared during the past decade¹⁻¹².

The present investigation deals with the study of mixed ligand complexes of copper(II) with ethylenediamine and aspirinate and evaluation of their formation constants by the method of Schaap

TABLE 1—DERIVED F_{11} FUNCTION FOR THE Cu(II)-ETHYLENEDIAMINE-ASPIRINATE SYSTEM

[Cu ²⁺]=0.5 mM [Aspirinate]=0.2 M		$\mu=1.5$ T=298 ± 1°K		$I_M=100$ Div. $-E_{1/2}(s)=0.0165V$		pH=5.6 A=326.16(Calcd.)	
[X] × 10 ⁶ (moles)	log $\frac{I_M}{I_C}$	$E_{1/2}$	$F_{00}[X] \times 10^{-9}$	$F_{10}[X] \times 10^{-14}$	$F_{20}[X] \times 10^{-20}$		
0.2948	0.0269	0.2845	0.9096	3.0855	1.6468		
0.5896	0.0362	0.2455	2.1890	3.7126	1.8870		
0.8844	0.0506	0.2524	3.8780	4.9792	2.0117		
1.1792	0.0757	0.2570	5.8716	4.9793	2.0177		
1.4739	0.0888	0.2610	8.2637	5.6066	2.0398		
1.7688	0.0969	0.2644	10.9710	6.2025	2.0866		
2.0636	0.1024	0.2675	14.1439	6.8539	2.0613		
2.3584	0.1106	0.2700	17.5169	7.4274	2.0468		

B=2.6 × 10¹⁴ and C_{av}=1.968 × 10²⁰.

and McMaster¹³. The formation constants in simple system have been calculated by the method of DeFord and Hume¹⁴ as well as by Mihailov's¹⁵ mathematical method and both the values agree well.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of reagent grade. The copper solution was prepared from copper sulphate. Sodium salt of aspirin was prepared with sodium hydroxide solution using Toshniwal pH meter. The ionic strength was maintained at 1.5 μ by adding the requisite amount of sodium perchlorate. The polarograms were taken at pH 5.6 adjusted by adding sodium hydroxide and perchloric acid. All the measurements were carried out at 25 ± 1°. Prior to the polarographic examination, purified and pre-saturated nitrogen gas was passed through the test solution (taken in H-type cell) for 20 min to expel dissolved oxygen. All the polarograms were taken on manual polarograph using polyflex spot galvanometer. The d.m.e. with the following characteristics ; m = 1.867 mg/sec, t = 3.5 sec/drop in open circuit, h = 50 cm was used throughout the course of the investigation.

The formation constants of the complexes of copper with ethylenediamine and with aspirinate were measured separately prior to the study of the mixed ligand system. The conditions used corresponded, as closely as possible, to those planned for the mixed systems. In the studies with ethylenediamine, all solutions contained 5 × 10⁻⁴ M Cu²⁺ and 0.001% "Triton X-100" as maxima suppressor. The concentration of "free" ethylenediamine (en) was calculated from the pH, and the total amount present from the appropriate pK values^{16,17} [pK₁=0.5, pK₂=9.48 for (en) and pK=4.57 for (asp)].

The copper(II)-ethylenediamine-aspirinate system was studied by keeping the concentration of the weaker ligand constant (aspirinate 0.2 M), while varying the concentration of ethylenediamine in each case (0.02-0.16 M).

Results and Discussion

Initially, polarograms were run at four different heights and their diffusion controlled nature is confirmed by the nature of the plots of i_d vs $\sqrt{h}$ (h = effective height of mercury column), which were linear and passed through the origin. Again, polarograms were run at four different concentrations and plots of i_d vs concentration were also linear.

The values of formation constants for simple systems have been evaluated by the method of DeFord and Hume as well as by Mihailov's mathematical method. In all cases a single well defined and diffusion controlled wave with a slope of 32 ± 2 mV was obtained on plotting E_{a.e.} against log [(i/i_d - i)], indicating the reduction to be reversible involving two electrons.

A cathodic shift in half wave potential on addition of ethylenediamine in the solution containing copper (complexed with aspirinate) was observed. The shift, however, is greater in presence of aspirinate than in its absence. This indicates the formation of mixed ligand complex of Cu(II) with ethylenediamine and aspirinate. The polarographic characteristics and F₁₁ functions of mixed Cu(II)-ethylenediamine-aspirinate system at one fixed aspirinate concentration of 0.2 M are summarised in Table 1. In this system Cu(II) forms only one mixed ligand species [Cu(en)(asp)]⁺ with $\beta_{1,1} = 12.95 \times 10^{14}$.

The equilibria among various complex species in the solution (at 25°) is schematically shown below.

Two main changes expected when we go from a simple (MX) to a ternary complex (MXY), are (i) structural changes (i.e. changes in geometry) and (ii) changes in bond energy and mutual interaction of ligands. The second effect may arise from the effects of solvent and ionic strength (as also from statistical effects), change in bond strength, and steric hindrance due to size of the ligand. In the present study the factors which might most probably affect the stability of these mixed complexes are statistical, electrostatic and steric. From a comparison of the dimensionless disproportionation constant K_s for the following equilibrium it is found that the mixed ligand complex is more stable than what might be expected from purely statistical considerations.

The enhanced stability might therefore be attributed to factors such as steric and electrostatic.

Acknowledgement

The financial support from C. S. I. R., New Delhi is gratefully acknowledged.

References

1. L. NEWMAN and D. N. HUMER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 79, 4571, 4781.
2. J. I. WATERS and J. MANSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 78, 2856.
3. G. SCHWARZENBACH and A. WILLI, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 528.
4. J. I. WATERS and R. D. WITT, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 82, 1933.
5. S. C. KHURANA and C. M. GUPTA, *Electrochim. Acta*, 1973, 18, 591.
6. S. C. BAGHEL, K. K. CHOUDHARY and J. N. GAUR, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1975, 37, 2513.
7. R. S. SHARMA and J. N. GAUR, *Trans. SAEST*, 1978, 13.
8. S. C. KHURANA and C. M. GUPTA, *Talanta*, 1972, 19, 1235.
9. S. C. KHURANA and C. M. GUPTA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1972, 34, 2557.
10. S. C. KHURANA and C. M. GUPTA, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1973, 35, 209.
11. S. C. KHURANA and C. M. GUPTA, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1975, 28, 1617.
12. M. S. VERMA, S. S. SINGH and H. L. NIGAM, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1979, 18A, 329.
13. W. B. SCHAAP and D. L. MCMASTER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 83, 4699.
14. D. D. DEFORD and D. N. HUMER, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 73, 5921.
15. M. H. MIHAILOV, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1974, 36, 107, 115, 141.
16. A. ALBERT and E. P. SERJEANT, "Ionisation Constants of Acids and Bases", 1962.
17. D. D. FERRIN and V. S. SHARMA, *J. Chem. Soc., A*, 1969, 2060.

Polarographic Study of Thorium(IV) and Uranyl(II) Complexes with DL-Ornithine Hydrochloride

R. S. SAXENA and S. P. BANSAL

Department of Chemistry, Malaviya Regional Engineering College, Jaipur-302 004

Manuscript received 15 January 1980, revised 13 March 1981, accepted 7 January 1982

AMINO acids have a wide variety of biological, pharmaceutical and other chemical uses, and have been reported to form complexes with some metals. Hence their importance has grown. The polarographic behaviour of some amino acids and their metal complexes have already been studied by Saxena *et al*¹⁻³.

This communication reports the polarographic behaviour of uranyl(II) and Th(IV) complexes with DL-ornithine hydrochloride, for which no reference could be found in the literature.

Thorium(IV) reduces irreversibly at d.m.e. in presence of DL-ornithine hydrochloride and produces a diffusion controlled wave. The values of kinetic parameters - transfer coefficient (α) and formal rate constant ($K'_{t,h}$) have been determined by Koutecky's method⁴ as extended by Meites and Israel⁵.

Uranyl(II) reduces reversibly at d.m.e. in presence of DL-ornithine hydrochloride and produces a diffusion controlled wave. The composition and stability constants of the metal complexes have been studied by Lingane method⁷.

Experimental

DL-Ornithine hydrochloride (DOH) was supplied by B. D. H. Chemicals Ltd., Poole, England and all other chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. Their solutions were prepared in double distilled conductivity water. Triton-X-100 (0.002 percent) was used as maxima suppressor. The ionic strength was maintained by NaClO₄.

Polarographic measurements were made on a Toshniwal polarograph, equipped with thermostated H-cell and saturated calomel electrode. Capillary had the characteristics in 0.1 M NaClO₄ at -0.5 volts vs S. C. E. with h_{H_2} value of 40 cm, $m = 2.895$ mg/sec, $t = 2.40$ seconds.

The values of kinetic parameters were determined from the polarograms of the solutions containing 0.1 m M Th⁴⁺, 0.1 M NaClO₄, 0.002 percent Triton-X-100 and various concentrations of DOH.

Results and Discussion

Uranyl-DOH complex at d.m.e. gives a well defined wave in aqueous medium. Reduction is found to be diffusion controlled one electron